

GLOSSOPHOBIA AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS IN KARACHI, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Speaking in front of an audience is a process, an act, and an art. The major goal of public speaking is to express one's thoughts and emotions in order to elicit the appropriate reaction. **Objective:** To determine the level of glossophobia among undergraduate nursing students in Karachi. **Methodology:** A cross sectional analysis were conducted. This study was completed within 6 months after the approval from the designated institution. Sample size was calculated by using software Open Epi version 3.0 and calculated sample size was 167 with a 95% confidence level and 5% of margin of error. A convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data. All Generic BSN student of 2nd, 3rd, and 4th year degree program were included and students of all other nursing disciplines were excluded. The data was collected by using an open excess, validated and structured questionnaire; the personal report of public speaking anxiety (PRPSA). **Results:** The findings revealed that the majority of participants (47.3%) exhibited a **low** level on the measured variable. A slightly lower proportion (44.9%) demonstrated a moderate level, while only a small number of participants (7.8%) scored at a high level. **Conclusion:** The findings of this study revealed that nursing students experience a relatively high level of public speaking anxiety, with notable variations based on gender and year of study. The findings underscore the need for targeted interventions especially during the early years of nursing education.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking in front of an audience is a process, an act, and an art. The major goal of public speaking is to express one's thoughts and emotions in order to elicit the appropriate reaction. Being able to communicate well in public is not a luxury but rather a requirement for students who will shortly graduate to work as secretaries and managers [1]. An excessive or

uncontrollable fear of a thing or circumstance is called a phobia. People who suffer from any kind of phobia also experience negative effects on their personal connections, lifestyle, and place of employment. Following traumatic brain injuries, despair, and substance addiction, there is a significant risk of developing phobias [2, 3]. It is a mental illness that

causes a person to be terrified or frightened to speak in front of others. The lack of training or preparation for public speaking is the root of this issue. Furthermore, the training typically lacks the ambiance or impression of public speaking [4]. People can often interact with society with ease; however, it is paradoxical that not everyone is able to give a speech or presentation in front of the public with accuracy and fluency because many people have encountered difficulties when doing so [5, 6]. Fear and anxiety may be the main obstacles preventing kids from learning and succeeding. This anxiety has historically been categorized as a social fear by communication researchers, Context-based anxiety of communication affects up to 82% of people worldwide, with more than 74% of the anxiety being specific to public speaking circumstances [7]. If the anxiety that students who are used to public speaking experience is mild or moderate, it shouldn't be a reason for alarm and may even motivate them to improve their learning. However, there will be adverse effects if the anxiety is felt at a high or extremely high level [8, 9]. These adverse consequences include a drop in learning motivation and academic achievement, stress, and even annoyance from not being used to new routines. Furthermore, kids may struggle to regulate their emotions, experience frequent physical and psychological symptoms, and experience a variety of issues with learning activities in the future. Everyday life involves stress and anxiety, and students are not immune to these emotional states. Students in school environments experience academic stress as an adaptive systemic process that is mostly psychological in nature in response to demands that are deemed stressful in the subject's assessment [10]. Two elements that affect students' academic lives include stress, which is a complex mental or emotional pressure brought on by outside forces, and glossophobia, which is the dread of public speaking [11]. According to studies, newly graduated nurses do not possess the levels of competency required in the real world of nursing practice to satisfy the constantly rising expectations in the complex healthcare system of today including best communication skills[12]. As educators and health advocates, healthcare students must be able to speak in front of an audience. Students must, however, have greater faith in their capacity to instruct in public. Additionally, students

feel nervous before giving a speech in front of an audience[13]. For nursing students, public speaking is crucial since they will be powerful health advocates in the future and speaking is one of their fundamental skills that will help them succeed in their careers[3]. One of the difficulties nursing students encounter in the classroom, in clinical settings, and in the community is public speaking anxiety [14]. This study aimed to determine the level of glossophobia among undergraduate nursing students at a public sector college of nursing at Karachi, Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive cross sectional study design was used for this study as this design were appropriate to determine the level of public speaking anxiety among nursing students

Setting and Sample

This study was completed within 6 months after the approval from the Research Committee, of Qatar College of Nursing and Midwifery, Karachi. Sample size was calculated by using software Open Epi version 3.0 and a previous study effect size 0.93 [15] was considered to calculate the sample size is 167 with a 95% confidence level and 5% of margin of error. A convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data. All Generic BSN student of 2nd year, 3rd year, and 4th year degree program were included in the study. All other nursing discipline students e.g. nurse aid nurse midwife and diploma nurse, CMW student and technician student was excluded.

Study Tool

The data was collected by using an open excess, validated and structured questionnaire; the personal report of public speaking anxiety (PRPSA). PRPSA scale was developed by McCroskey 2013, [16]. Containing 34 items. Each item on a scale rated as comprising, strongly disagree (1point), disagree (2 point), neutral (3 point), agree (4 point), (5 point) strongly agree.

Baseline Characteristics of the Study Participants

This questionnaire assessed the characteristics of the study participants. It assessed age, academic year, semester, gender, whether the respondents lived with

family or friends, whether they attended a government or international high school.

Consistency and Reliability

Cronbach's α values were used to assess the instruments' internal consistency and reliability; $\alpha > 0.80$ denoted acceptable consistency. Convergent validity was tested by assessing the correlation of each item with the overall scale.

Data Collection Procedure

The data were collected by using structured questionnaires, which included the socio-demographic, PRPSA. After obtaining the necessary ethical approval to conduct the study and permission to use the instruments from the copyright holders, the questionnaires were distributed in written. The participants were informed about the inclusion criteria at the beginning of the survey to ensure that they met the required criteria. A socio-demographic questionnaire and a psychometric instruments were used to collect the required data.

Ethical Considerations

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the participants

Variables	f (%)
Gender	
Male	79 (47.3)
Female	88 (52.7)
Age	
19-25	82 (49.1)
Above 25	85 (50.9)
Last School Attended	
Govt.	82 (49.1)
Private	54 (32.3)
International School	31 (18.6)
Living Status	
Family	68 (40.7)
Relatives and Friends	48 (28.7)
At Campus (Hostel)	33 (19.8)
Alone	18 (10.8)
Academic Year	
3 rd Year	67 (40.1%)
4 th Year	100 (59.9%)

Before the data collection, approval of the study was taken from the concern institute of nursing. Furthermore, all participants were required to sign a written informed consent and oral information was provided regarding the study and right to withdraw from the study without any penalty. Privacy and confidentiality of the participants were kept protected, ID codes were assigned to the individual information of the participants.

RESULTS

Table 1 displays demographic characteristics of the study participants. Most of the participants were female (52.7%), while 47.3% of the participants were male. According to the age study subjects were evenly distributed, with 49.1% aged 19-25 years and 50.9% aged above 25. Regarding the type of last school attended, 49.1% of participants came from government schools, 32.3% from private schools, and 18.6% from international schools. In terms of living status, 40.7% of students lived with their families, 28.7% with relatives or friends, 19.8% stayed at campus hostels, and 10.8% lived alone. As for academic year distribution, 59.9% of the students were in their 4th year, while 40.1% were in the 3rd year.

Table 2 Demonstrates the level of public speaking anxiety, the findings revealed that the majority of participants (n = 79, 47.3%) exhibited a **low** level on the measured variable. A slightly lower proportion (n = 75, 44.9%) demonstrated a **moderate** level, while

only a small number of participants (n = 13, 7.8%) scored at a **high** level. These results indicate that most participants fall within the low to moderate range, with relatively few achieving high levels.

Table 2: Levels of Pubic Speaking Anxiety

Levels	f (%)
Low	79 (47.3)
Moderate	75(44.9)
High	13 (7.8)

Table 3 describes the association of demographic characteristics with PRPSA, was analyzed by applying Chi-Square and Fisher Exact test. No any statistical association was found between any of the demographic variables with PRPSA. According to gender basis, 53.2% of the total participants has low level of speaking anxiety. Notably, on the basis of living status the proportion of participants living

alone were markedly reported 61.1%, moderate level of public speaking anxiety but no any statistical association found. Surprisingly, according to academic year, only 6% of the participants from 4th year were reported high level of public speaking anxiety.

Table 3: Association of Demographic Characteristics with PRPSA Levels

Characteristics	Levels of Public Speaking Anxiety			p-value
	High	Low	Moderate	
Gender				0.241 ^a
Male	4 (5.1%)	42 (53.2%)	33 (41.8%)	
Female	9 (10.2%)	37 (42.0%)	42 (47.7%)	
Age				0.422 ^a
19-25	6 (7.3%)	43 (52.4%)	33 (40.2%)	
Above 25	7 (8.2%)	36 (42.4%)	42 (49.4%)	
Last School Attended				0.542 ^b
Govt.	5 (6.1%)	43 (52.4%)	41.5%)	
Private	5 (9.3%)	25 (46.3%)	24 (44.4%)	
International School	3 (9.7%)	11 (35.5%)	17 (54.8%)	
Living Status				0.153 ^a
Family	5 (7.4%)	35 (51.5%)	28 (41.2%)	
Relatives and Friends	6 (12.5%)	24 (50.0%)	18 (37.5%)	
At Campus (Hostel)	0 (0%)	15 (45.5%)	18 (54.5%)	
Alone	2 (11.1%)	5 (27.8%)	11 (61.1%)	
Academic Year				0.574 ^a
3 rd Year	7 (10.4%)	31 (46.3%)	29 (43.3%)	
4 th Year	6 (6.0%)	48 (48.0%)	46 (46.0%)	

^a Pearson chi-square ^b Fisher's Exact

DISCUSSION

Almost everyone struggles with public speaking anxiety; this illogical block of speaking in front of an audience has become commonplace [17]. In the current study level of public speaking anxiety among nursing students were assessed were 47.3% participants reported low 7.8% demonstrated high and rest of the participants had moderate level of glossophobia. Dissimilarly a study conducted by Anagalligo in 2021 in Finland reported 50 % of high level of public speaking anxiety among university students [18]. Another study conducted by Waraporn in Thailand in 2020 reported 31.0% high and 26.0% low level of anxiety among graduate students [19]. In the current study male participants reported less (5.1%) while female reported more (10.2%) of high level of glossophobia. Findings suggesting that females often report higher levels of communication apprehension and anxiety in evaluative situations. Several factors may contribute to this discrepancy, including societal expectations, gender norms, and differences in self-perception and confidence levels. These results suggest a need for gender-sensitive interventions and support systems that address the unique challenges female nursing students may face regarding public speaking and performance-related stress. In contrary another study revealed no statistically significance difference between gender group [20]. In this study 47.3% participants were male and 52.7 % were female similarly another study conducted in 2024 by Ali where the female participants were (51.9%) and male participants were (48.1%) [21]. On the bases of academic year 4th year students surprisingly reported the lowest level (6%) of public speaking anxiety, this may be due to repeated exposure can help desensitize them to the stress of public speaking. By their final year, nursing students have had more opportunities to engage in patient communication, classroom presentations, and inter-professional collaboration. Another study conducted in Indonesia in 2022 by Rahman revealed the comparable findings, male participants in this study reported lower levels of anxiety than female ones [22]. Correspondingly, Megha yadav from USA in 2022 reported comparable findings where female participants reported higher level of public speaking anxiety than the male ones [23]. Research suggests females are more likely to engage in self-critical

thinking and perfectionist tendencies, which can exacerbate anxiety when speaking in front of others due to fear of making mistakes [24].

Conclusion

The findings of this study reveal that nursing students experience a relatively high level of public speaking anxiety, with notable variations based on gender and year of study. Female students reported higher levels of glossophobia compared to their male counterparts, and second- and third-year students exhibited greater anxiety than those in their final year. These results suggest that public speaking anxiety is a prevalent issue among nursing students, potentially impacting their academic performance and future professional communication. The findings underscore the need for targeted interventions—such as communication skills training, anxiety-reduction workshops, and confidence-building activities—especially during the early years of nursing education.

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